

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE TECHNOLOGY OF MASTERING THE CONCEPT OF "LENGTH" IN I CLASSES OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Among the problems of didactics, the need to "achieve the perfection of the methodical system of teaching this or that subject, to make it adequate to the convocations of the industrial revolutions" has always been relevant, and even today, the formation of an educational space that transforms the characteristics of the IV industrial revolution is an important and urgent problem. It also makes researches about the model of "methodical system" aimed at solving the mentioned problem relevant. Which in these research processes are necessary elements to determine the nomenclature and classification of teaching tools, the scientific-theoretical and technological features of their application according to the logic of the modern teaching process of various subjects. The elementary course of mathematics is also an integrative course in its content, which follows from the objectives of teaching mathematics in elementary grades. Thus, in addition to arithmetic material (basic material), elements of algebra, geometry, physics, astronomy and natural science are also included in the mathematics course of grades I-IV, and concepts, definitions, rules and properties related to these elements are mainly taught to students at an intuitive level. It is obvious that the fields of science that we mentioned are directly related to quantities. The subject of mathematics is closely related to quantities and their measurement. Despite what has been said, we claim the relevance of conducting research on the topic "Technology of application of the "problem task type" to the management of the process of teaching Mathematics in secondary schools".

Keywords: methodical system, measurement, measurement skills, quantities, length, method of teaching length, conventional measurement units, method of teaching centimeter.

The actuality of the subject. Measuring skills and measuring tools are widely used in everyday life. Measurement provides a link between different areas of mathematics. For example, when measuring, there is a very close connection between number concepts and spatial concepts. From this point of view, the "Measurement" section in the 1st grade includes a wide application of numbers and addition-subtraction operations on numbers. In the first class, the measurement of quantities such as length, mass, capacity and time and various related problems are given.

Solving these problems serves to reinforce the skills taught throughout the year, as well as to improve skills related to elementary algebra (finding the unknown, how long, how short, heavy-light, scale model, etc.). The formation of students' measurement skills is mainly carried out in 5 stages:

1. *Determination of the quantity to be measured.*
2. *Comparison and ranking (comparison of objects to be measured with others).*
3. *Measurement with non-standard (conventional) units.*
4. *Measurement with standard units.*
5. *Application.*

The importance of teaching quantities in primary grades is as follows:

- the knowledge and habits gained by students are directly related to life;
- by learning the basic quantities, they prepare for the next stages of education;
- familiarity with quantities develops students' spatial imagination;

- by learning to measure quantities, they gain practical knowledge and skills necessary for life;

- by measuring the quantities, students' ideas about numbers and arithmetic operations are broadened and deepened.

Every teacher should pay attention to some points when teaching quantities in the first grade: before measuring different quantities, it is important to get acquainted with certain characteristics of these quantities; for example, a child should know that the length of a pencil does not change when it is taken out of the bag and placed on the table, or when you take apples from the basket, the mass of the basket decreases. How much liquid a container holds is measured by its capacity, and different containers can have the same capacity. Also, in the city where you live, the clock shows the same time everywhere - at home and at school: if the clock at home shows 1 o'clock, then it is 1 o'clock at school. For this purpose, in order to better understand the characteristics of quantities, students should be given tasks of different nature.

Literacy competence, which is one of the competencies defined for a person of the 21st century, requires the formation of the ability to understand and interpret information, facts, emotions, and ideas presented in written and oral form, as well as to express them orally and in writing. : "Length", "long-short", "same length", "weight", "heavy-light", The correct expression of concepts such as "capacity", "wide-narrow", "time", "before-after", as well as their standard measurement units taught in the 1st grade (centimeter, kilogram, liter and hour) should be in focus.

Before starting the teaching of this subject, students should have mastered the skills of number representation and addition-subtraction up to 20 in the number axis.

It should not be overlooked that the connection between different subjects is ensured under the "Measurements" content line, since integration in the lesson helps students to gain a wider and deeper understanding by combining the knowledge of different subjects, and makes the learning process of students more interesting and effective. Thus, measurement and evaluation are used in various subjects, including physical education, visual arts, technology, music, and life sciences.

Children's first intuitive ideas about length (distance) begin to form in the preschool period. Ideas about the geometric dimensions of an object, i.e. its length, width, height, wide, narrow, thick, thin, tall, short, etc., are formed and developed starting from the preschool period. In the first grade, this process is further deepened. It should be noted that the color, shape, and material from which the objects are made gradually fade into the background and are isolated from the observation and comparison. Items are compared by length.

Now let's get acquainted with the method of teaching length. In the first grade, students should acquire the following learning outcomes:

- Estimates which of two or more given objects is longer or shorter without using measurements (4.1.2).
- Given objects are "tall", "short", "tall", "short", "about the same length", etc. according to their length. compares with words (4.1.2).
- Selects a convenient conventional unit of measurement (clamp, cuboid, inch, foot, step, etc.) to measure the length of an object (4.2.1).
- Compares the length of objects using conventional units of measurement (4.1.2).
- Estimates which of the given objects are long-short, heavy-light, wide-narrow (1.3.5).
- Explains that a ruler is used to measure length and draw lines (4.2.2).
- Measure the length of a given piece with a ruler (4.2.2).
- Draws a line of given length using a ruler (4.2.3).
- Describes addition and subtraction problems in mathematical expressions (2.1.3).
- Apply addition and subtraction skills in a circle of 20 to find length in simple problems (4.2.1).

Research shows that the principle of visibility is assessed by new dimensions of pedagogical thinking. The principle of objectivity does not simply deny the function and role of visibility in the learning process, but interprets them in the course of the formation of new theoretical thinking. Violation of the principle of visibility in training can negatively affect the effectiveness of the teaching process. The principle of visibility requires that the learned information be presented in a concrete, clear and visualized way. That is why various aids should be used in the learning process: a ruler, colored tape and strips, colored pencils, various objects for measuring.

4 hours have been allocated for teaching the subject. In the lesson, students get acquainted with the concept of "length", they get the ability to compare the

lengths of objects. During the comparison, the expressions "longer", "shorter", "same" are used. When teaching the subject, the teacher should pay attention to some elements: In order to master the measurement skills, first of all, the skills of comparing quantities should be formed. For this purpose, "What is the length?", "Which is longer?", "Which is shorter?", "Which objects are the same length?" questions are clarified. It is very important to expect such consistency when examining questions. Clamps, cubes and other various measuring tools should be prepared before the lesson in order to use different conventional measurement units.

The teacher can start the lesson by comparing the lengths of different objects in the classroom. For example, pen and book, desk and board, etc. Comparisons can also be made between students, for example: girls with long and short hair, tall and short boys can be compared. In the lesson, pairs are assigned to distribute colored strips of different lengths prepared in advance and compare their lengths.

As we know, the student's cognitive activity is closely related to his asking a question and searching for the correct answer to that question. Conscious activity, regulation of one's own activity, evaluation and reference to the obtained results are related to this issue. One of the main conditions for the development of the student's logical thinking is that he formulates questions and answers them logically. So, at the research-discussion stage, it is necessary to direct the task in such a way that the student is involved in cognitive activity.

- Grandmother Aynur and Elkhana knitted a scarf. Whose scarf is longer? How to determine this?

A relevant image is displayed. In the research task, scarves can be compared according to the number of stripes. I would also like to mention that this task can be done with the whole class with the help of various objects (small ribbons, strips cut from colored paper, pencils, etc.).

In the further continuation of the educational process, students' performance of the following practical task has a positive effect on their preparation, which the generalization of the obtained materials leads us to this conclusion: 2-3 pencils of different lengths are placed on the table. A student is brought in front of the board and his eyes are covered with a handkerchief. The student arranges several pencils by hand on the table according to their length. The pupil's eyes are opened and the correctness of the sequence is checked.

The procedure for comparing objects by their length and measuring their length is explained. It is noted that the unit of measurement is used to measure.

A teacher must plan a lesson that correctly identifies the content, activities used to learn, or appropriate expectations for students at different levels to be successful so that differentiation can occur. Research shows that differentiated instruction is effective for gifted students as well as students with disabilities.

When students are given more choices about how they can learn the material, they feel more responsible for their own learning. Since the teachers organize the learning process according to the learning needs of the students, it is observed that there are less order-discipline problems in the classrooms, instead, it seems that the students are more engaged in learning. Thus, in

teaching the subject, the teacher should take into account the above, both in the guide stage and in the tasks for independent work.

At the next stage of the lesson, the students can be given the following task. The task can be performed with the whole class. The teacher should act as a facilitator and guide the students.

The task can be performed visually (approximate) first. As confirmation of the comparison, the numbers showing their lengths are compared. The main goal in these tasks is to form estimation skills. It is necessary to pay attention to the sequence of tasks. 1. The lengths are first determined roughly, and then sorted from longest to shortest. 2. In this task, students first estimate the length and then check it.

Conventional units of measurement should be explained as learning material. However, there are points that the teacher should pay attention to when teaching these concepts. So what are they? Let's take a look: As we know, using conventional measurement units in measurement is one of the important skills needed in everyday life. For example, we often measure the width of the door in inches to determine whether any item will pass, or determine the location of the refrigerator based on our height. Using conventional units of measurement is a preliminary step to using standard units of measurement. In this regard, attention should be paid to the expectation of consistency.

An important task of the training process is to support the student during training and improve his training results.

The training model of subjects is based on the model "Learn → reinforce → apply".

Learn - mastery of knowledge and skills with visual aids enriched with illustrative materials.

Consolidate – improving new acquired knowledge and skills through exercises, studies, writing and other ways.

Apply – applying learned knowledge and skills to increasingly complex problem solving and modeling. Each subject is taught on the basis of a five-step learning cycle. Problem solving is of exceptional importance in the teaching of mathematics, as we and other theorists and practitioners have repeatedly emphasized. In general, the term "mathematical problem" refers to those issues that arise both within mathematics and outside it, which are expressed in "mathematical language" and are solved by mathematical methods and tools. These issues have different contents and may be related to other fields of science, life, and daily practical activities.

It is a pity that in textbooks containing problems and examples, we rarely find issues that have content related to life events and other fields of science that are outside the content. However, such problems not only reveal the connection of mathematics with life and other sciences, but also require converting it into mathematical language, which itself helps to develop a certain creative ability. The topic begins with problem solving and ends with problem solving.

In general, it is important to distinguish between the concepts of "problem solving" and "teaching problem solving." In this regard, it is recommended to approach the 4-phase cognitive process (understanding - planning - solving - checking) as a three-stage student activity in the educational process. teaching problem solving is realized in three stages: involvement, brainstorming and discussion.

During the teaching of length, it is planned to give such a problem at the application stage (the problem is intended to form students' estimation skills using conventional measurement units):

Problem: The picture shows a tape and a clamp. Students have to find approximately how many clamps the tape has.

It is very important to follow the sequence to solve the problem. First, the students themselves estimate the length of the tape. Then they review the answer options and mark the option closest to their own (for example, Pomegranate). At the last stage, they check their answers with a tool equal to the length of the clamp (for example, the width of a finger or the tip of a pencil, etc.).

Mathematical games are one of the most effective methods in teaching mathematics, which help to develop the student's interest in learning and to master the subject. It's fun for kids and a way to make learning more efficient for the teacher. Especially in mathematics classes, the role of mathematical games is very important in preventing the mental fatigue of students, so that the lesson is not boring.

Guided by what we have said, during the teaching of the topic, "Who will find it right?" the game can be played:

Rules of the game:

1. An object that can be measured in the room and a suitable measurement unit (clamp, cube, square, foot) are selected.

2. Players estimate and record the length of the object.

3. The length of the item is measured with the selected measurement unit.

4. The player who guesses the closest to the correct answer gets 1 point.

The game can be played in class or after school.

Such a task can be given to work at home, which students can be given such a task: choose 4-5 objects at home. Then the sheet is filled in the order indicated. Students bring it to the next class.

To ensure interdisciplinary integration, it is necessary to focus on the fact that measurement skills are widely used in physical education, technology, fine arts. "Long-short", "tall-short" etc. words should be used.

In the 3rd hour of teaching the subject, students get acquainted with centimeters as a standard unit of length. Takes measurements using a ruler, draws a piece of a given length, compares the length of pieces with measurements, solves various length problems to improve addition-subtraction skills.

When introducing the first standard unit of measurement, the centimeter, in first grade, the teacher should consider some issues: Correct use of measuring tools is one of the important measurement skills. The simplest measuring tool students encounter is a ruler. In this regard, students are first introduced to centimeters. Standard units of measurement are units used in a certain system of units (centimeter, kilogram, liter, hour). Conventional units are any units that are convenient for the user depending on certain conditions (for example: inches, steps for measuring length; cubes for measuring weight; cups, cups for measuring volume).

As the first stage of the lesson, the teacher can measure the edge of the table and write the result on the board in order to direct the students' attention to the lesson and to make them more active. Then one of the students measures the length of the table with his inch and the result of the measurement is again written on the board. The teacher asks why the two numbers are different. Students' answers are listened to.

It is appropriate to ask such an issue at the research discussion stage:

- Lala measured the edge in inches to decorate the photo album. He asked his younger brother to cut a ribbon 3 inches long. Lala saw that the tape was short. What do you think is the reason for the tape being short?

A discussion is organized around the question in the task. Different questions explain the meaning of standard units of measurement. It is explained that a ruler is a tool for measuring the length of objects. Students are taught the basic skills of using a ruler.

Drawing a piece of fabric to a given length in first grade is one of the skills that students struggle with the

most. It is more appropriate to form it in several stages: 1) first, the ability to draw a straight line should be formed. For this, fun tasks can be given, such as drawing colored lines using different pencils; 2) and then they are instructed to mark two points at a certain distance. This can also be given in a fun way; for example: "First, make a dot with a blue pencil. Measure 3 centimeters and make a point with a red pencil"; 3) at the last stage, these two points are connected. Each stage is repeated several times.

Each of the action steps can be repeated several times separately to draw a given length of fabric to provide differential training. You may be asked to draw a piece that consists of several parts; for example, "Take a red cloth 2 cm long and a blue cloth 4 cm long from its end. What is the total length of these pieces?"

Students are instructed to cut different lengths of colored strips at home. The cut strips are glued to a sheet of checkered notebook. The length in centimeters is written below.

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